

Review Article

Review Article On Medicinal Plant Aloe

Sandip Gorade*¹, Sonali Kalam², Dr. Gajanan Sanap³

Department of Pharmacy, LBYP College Of D.Pharmacy, Pathri, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18 Nov 2023

Accepted: 20 Nov 2023

Published: 29 Nov 2023

Keywords:

Aloe

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10219050

ABSTRACT

The aim of this review project is to represent the concise review on the Functional and Pharmacognostic role of Aloe including their general introduction, history. Morphology of plant etc. Moreover, in this project we aim to give the brief information about Macroscopic and Microscopic characteristics of Aloe, in addition to this, their chemical constituents, specific chemical test, traditional uses of Aloe, and marketed formulations. However, our intention is to update the pharmacological current activity of Aloe and their cosmetic application. The main objective of the present study of morphological, functional, constitutional, Nature of Aloe. Identify the properties of Aloe. Different marketed Preparation of Aloe, Medicinal uses of Aloe mainly used in the Cosmetics. Herbal use of Aloe

INTRODUCTION

People have been using and knowing about the health, beauty, and skin advantages of aloe vera for millennia. The Arabic term Aloe vera, meaning "shining bitter substance," is derived from the Latin vera, meaning "true." 2,000 years ago, Greek scientists thought aloe vera was a panacea. The Egyptians referred to aloe as "the plant of immortality. Aloe vera is a plant that is used in dermatology nowadays for a variety of treatments.

One of the significant nosocomial pathogens causing severe infections, particularly in hospitalized patients in burn wards, is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*). [1]. Numerous nosocomial infections, including urinary or wound infections, bacteremia, endocarditis, and in some cases mortality, are

*Corresponding Author: Sandip Gorade

Address: Department of Microbiology, Ashokrao Mane Institute of Pharmacy, Ambap-416112, India.

Email ✉: sahilagarwal1912@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

brought on by this opportunistic and extremely resistant bacteria. Infections with *P. aeruginosa* are linked to higher rates of death and morbidity in immunocompromised, disabled, cystic fibrosis, and hospitalized burn patients. [1, 2]. Invasive operations are mostly attributed to the widespread and unselective use of antibiotics. As a result, the rapid emergence of numerous resistances among *P. aeruginosa* isolates in the clinical settings has been facilitated by the development of resistance mechanisms.

History

Greece, Egypt, India, Mexico, Japan, and China are just a many of the societies that have employed aloe vera for remedial purposes formillennia. Nefertiti and Cleopatra, two Egyptian queens, employed it as a regular part of their beauty rules. It was used to cure dogfaces' injuries by Alexander the Great and Christopher Columbus. John Goodyew's restatement of Dioscorides' medical book *De Materia Medica* in bulletin 1655 contained the first citation of aloe vera in English..2 Aloe vera was already being used in America as a laxative by the early 1800s, but in the middle of the 1930s, something changed when it was successfully utilized to treat chronic and severe radiation dermatitis. Around 3000 B.C., aloe vera is mentioned in Chinese and Sumerian texts. Aloe vera has long been referred to as the "flower of the desert" in Arabic culture. Aloe vera was first sold in the Middle East by Arabs. Places like India, China, and Malaysia have recognized its medical value.

a. Location of Aloes

Aloe, which has 500 species, is wide and is regarded as an invasive species in numerous corrid of the world. It's an evergreen imperishable that's native to the Arabian Peninsula but thrives untamed in dry, tropical, and tropical surroundings each over the world.

b. Biological sources:

- Aloe barbadensis miller is the botanical name for aloe.
- The dried latex of aloe vera plants is its biological source.
- Other names for it include socotrine aloe, cape aloe, and curacao aloe.
- It is a member of the family Liliaceae.

Morphological features:

- It is a perennial evergreen plant that is succulent in nature.
- It is a plant with few or no stems.
- It may grow to a height of 60 to 100 cm.
- It has meaty, thick leaves.
- The leaves have tiny white teeth and a serrated margin.
- Leaves have a rosette-shaped structure.
- A significant amount of pulp can be found in the leaf parenchyma.
- The base's breadth is 10 cm.
- The blossoms have a 90-cm diameter.
- The golden, 2-3 cm long tubular corolla of flowers.
- The blossom might be white, yellow, orange, or even crimson in hue.
- Dry capsules are used to store seeds.
- The calyx is absent.
- Roots spread out in the earth, not going too deep.
- An arbuscular mycorrhiza is formed by roots.

C. Plant

Aloe barbadensis miller is the name of the factory that produces aloe vera. It's a shrubby or arborescent, imperishable, xerophytic, succulent, pea-green factory that's a member of the Liliaceae family. Africa, Asia, Europe, and America's dry

climates are where it primarily grows. Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Tamil Nadu are among the Indian countries that have it.

d. Anatomy

The plant produces fleshy, triangular leaves with serrated edges, yellow tubular blooms, and fruits with numerous seeds. Each leaf is composed of three layers:

- 1) An interior clear gel comprised of glucomannans, amino acids, lipids, sterols, and vitamins comprises 99% water.
- 2) The anthraquinones and glycosides found in the middle layer of latex, which is the acrid yellow sap.
- 3) The rind is the thick, outer layer of 15 to 20 cells that serves as a protective covering and produces proteins and carbs. Vascular bundles located inside the rind are in charge of moving materials like water (xylem) and starch (phloem).

e. Active components with its properties:

There are seventy-five potentially active ingredients in aloe vera, including vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, amino acids, and salicylic acids.⁴⁻⁶

1. **Vitamins:** It contains the antioxidant vitamins A (beta-carotene), C, and E. There's also folic acid, vitamin B12, and choline. Antioxidants derail free revolutionaries.
2. **Enzymes:** It contains eight different enzymes, including cellulase, lipase, peroxidase, amylase, bradykinase, carboxypeptidase, catalase, and aliase. Bradykinase, when applied topically to the skin, helps reduce excessive inflammation while other enzymes help break down fats and sugars.
3. **Minerals:** Zinc, potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, selenium, copper, chromium, and other minerals are available. While not all of them are antioxidants, they are all required for the correct functioning of several enzyme systems.
4. **Sugars:** Monosaccharides, such as glucose and fructose, and polysaccharides, such as glucomannans and polymannose, are sugars. They are called mucopolysaccharides and come from

the plant's mucilage layer. Mannose-6-phosphate is the most common monosaccharide, and glucomannans, or beta-(1,4)-acetylated mannan, are the most common polysaccharides. It offers Acemannan, a well-known glucomannan that has also been discovered. Aloe vera gel has recently been used to isolate C-glucosyl chromone, a novel anti-inflammatory compound, and alprogen, a glycoprotein with antiallergic qualities.⁽⁷⁻⁸⁾

5. Anthraquinones: 12 anthraquinones, phenolic compounds with the septic and analgesic qualities, are present. commonly referred to as laxatives. Aloin and emodin have antiviral, antibacterial, and analgesic properties.

6. Fatty acids: It contains four plant steroids: lupeol, cholesterol, campesterol, and β -sisosterol. Each of these has an anti-inflammatory effect, and lupeol additionally has an

7. Hormones: Gibberellins and auxins, which have anti-inflammatory and wound-healing properties.

4. Other: It offers seven of the eight essential amino acids and twenty of the twenty-two amino acids that humans need. Salicylic acid, which has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities, is another ingredient in it. When added to topical preparations, the inert substance lignin improves the other ingredients' ability to penetrate the skin. About 3% of the gel is made up of soapy substances called saponins, which have antiseptic and cleansing qualities.

Mechanism of actions

1. Healing properties:

The fibroblast's growth factor receptors are contacted by the mannose-rich polysaccharide glucomannan. And the growth hormone gibberellin, which stimulates the fibroblast's activity and proliferation. This, in turn, greatly boosts collagen synthesis following topical and oral Aloe vera treatment.⁽⁹⁾ Aloe gel improved the amount of collagen in the wound while also altering its composition to include more type III

collagen and strengthening its cross-linking. As a result, it quickened the healing process and raised the scar tissue's breaking strength.(10). After oral or topical treatment, there has been a report of increased synthesis of hyaluronic acid and dermatan sulfate in the granulation tissue of a healing wound.(11)

2. Effects on skin exposure to UV and gamma radiation: There have been reports that aloe vera gel protects the skin from radiation damage. (12,13) The exact function of metallothionein, an antioxidant protein produced in the skin after aloe vera gel administration, is unknown. It scavenges hydroxyl radicals and keeps the skin's glutathione peroxidase and superoxide dismutase from being suppressed. It inhibits the generation and release of immunosuppressive cytokines derived from skin keratinocytes, including interleukin-10 (IL-10), thereby averting UV-induced suppression of delayed type hypersensitivity.(14)

3. Anti-inflammatory action:

Aloe vera lowers the synthesis of prostaglandin E2 from arachidonic acid and inhibits the cyclooxygenase pathway. C-glucosyl chromone, a novel anti-inflammatory compound, was recently extracted from gel extracts.(7)

4. Immune system effects:

Alprogen prevents calcium from entering mast cells, which prevents mast cell release of histamine and leukotriene through the antigen-antibody process.7. In a research using mice that had earlier received a murine Sarcoma cells are stimulated by acemannan to produce and release interleukin-1 (IL-1) and tumor necrosis factor from macrophages in mice. This triggered an immune response that led to the cancerous cells' necrosis and regression.(15). It is also possible for a number of low-molecular-weight substances to prevent activated human neutrophils from releasing reactive oxygen free radicals.(16)

4. Laxative effects: Latex contains anthraquinones, which are strong laxatives.

Intestinal peristalsis, mucus secretion, and water content are all increased by it.1.

5. Antiviral and antitumor activity: Direct or indirect effects could be the cause of these actions. The immune system's stimulation causes an indirect effect, while anthraquinones have a direct effect. Herpes simplex, varicella zoster, influenza, and other enveloped viruses are rendered inactive by anthraquinone aloin.(18)Recent research has demonstrated that a polysaccharide fraction inhibits benzopyrene's ability to bind to primary rat hepatocytes, thereby avoiding the formation of benzopyrene-DNA adducts that may initiate cancer. Furthermore, reports of an increase in glutathione S-transferase and a decrease in phorbol myristic acetate's tumor-promoting properties point to the potential advantages of aloe gel in the chemoprevention of cancer(19,20)

6. Moisturizing and anti-aging effect:

Mucopolysaccharides aid in the skin's capability to retain humidity. The product of collagen and elastin filaments by aloe stimulates fibroblast, which makes the skin less wrinkled and further elastic. also, by binding the superficially unloading epidermal cells together, it has cohesive goods that soften the skin. Zinc works as an tanga to strain pores, and amino acids also soften hardened skin cells. Aloe vera gel gloves have also been studied for their moisturizing parcels in the treatment of dry skin brought on by occupational exposure; in these cases, the skin integrity, fine wrinkle appearance, and erythema were each bettered.(21) It has an anti-acne effect as well.

7. Antiseptic effect: Aloe vera contains 6 antiseptic agents: Lupeol, salicylic acid, urea nitrogen, cinnamonic acid, phenols and sulfur. They all have inhibitory action on fungi, bacteria and viruses.

Cultivation and Collection:

It is a perennial evergreen that grows slowly to 0.8 m by 1 m. The plant can grow in soil with low nutrients, but it prefers light (sandy) and medium

(loamy) soils that drain well. Acidic, neutral, and basic (alkaline) soils are preferred by the plant. In the shadows, it cannot thrive. It can withstand drought and grows in either wet or dry soil. These plants are xerophytic. Seeds can be used to spread it. In the spring, seeds are sown in a warm green house. At 16°C, the seed typically germinates in 1-6 months. The seedlings are moved to pots with soil that drains properly. For their first two winters, at least, they are permitted to grow in a sunny location. Typically, the offsets will be accessible in the spring. When it's warm enough to promote new root growth and enable plant reestablishment, offsets can be freely produced by the plants and divided at any time of the year. Following the rainy season, young offsets are planted in rows 60 centimeters apart in the soil. Because leaves are spiky, the indigenous people gather leaves in the second year by covering their hands. To prepare the aloe, the leaves are chopped close to the base, stored in kerosene tins, and transported to a central location. Aloe vera juice is found in parenchymatous pericycle cells, which are mucilage cells. Mucilage cells press against pericycle cells in a single incision, causing the entire leaf juice to drain out.

Preparation of Aloe

a. Curacao or barbados aloe

The chopped leaves in the West Indies are arranged with their cut surfaces facing inward on the sides of a V-shaped vessel that is about 1-2 meters long. The juice that flows from the leaves is collected in a tin vessel that is positioned beneath the V-shaped vessel. This collected juice is then concentrated, either by boiling it until it has the consistency of thick honey, or by letting it evaporate naturally. These circumstances are favorable for barbaloin crystallization, and the aloe has barbaloin crystals in it, which causes it to become opaque and give rise to the name "hepatic" or "livery" aloe. After it cools, it's poured into boxes, gourds, or other handy containers.

b. Socotrine aloe

Once prepared, it is typically poured into goatskin bags, which are then packed into cases after a month or so of spontaneous evaporation until the mixture thickens and becomes pasty. In Europe, it is heated to a temperature of about 10% moisture and dried in wooden pans.

c. Zanzibar aloe

Like Socotrine aloe, this aloe is prepared similarly. It is enclosed in the hides of meat-eating animals. Monkey skin aloe is another name for this aloe.

d. Cape aloe

The plants that yield the leaves for Cape aloe are chopped off close to the stem and arranged around a hole dug in the ground where a sheepskin is spread out, smooth side facing up. After the leaves have yielded enough juice, the juice is concentrated using heat in iron cauldrons and then poured into boxes or skins where it cools and solidifies. The drug is exported in large quantities from Mossel Bay and Cape Town.

Characteristics of aloes

a. Curacao aloe

It is typically opaque and ranges in color from rich reddish brown to black to a brilliant yellowish-ish hue. It can occasionally be vitreous, in which case the tiny fragments are transparent and have a deep garnet-red color. After that, it is referred to as "Capey Barbados" and is worth less, but keeping it could make it more opaque and valuable. Curacao Aloes have an unpleasant, overpowering smell in addition to the queasy, bitter taste that all aloes have in common. It contains 12% of moisture and no more than 30% of substances that are insoluble in water. It is almost entirely soluble in 60% alcohol. It shouldn't produce more ash than 3%. There is a waxy fracture.

Fig. Aloe Vera

b. Socotrine aloes

Its unique scent is the main way it can be identified from Curacao Aloes. A large portion of the dry drug is opaque, with a color ranging from yellow-brown to dark brown, and is characterized by the presence of tiny cavities in the fractured surface. The taste is bitter and the fracture is uneven and porous.

c. Zanzibar aloes

In contrast to Socotrine Aloes, which are almost smooth and even, Zanzibar Aloes are typically imported in liver-brown masses that break with a dull, waxy fracture. They also frequently resemble Curacao in appearance. It tastes bitter and has a nice smell.

d. Cape aloes

It forms dark colored masses that fracture cleanly like glass and show a yellowish, reddish-brown, or greenish tinge in their splinters.

Macroscopic Characteristics

Plants: Perennials; stems 1.5 M. (5°) high, woody, rough from leaf-remnants; leaves laucous-green, often wit spots, thick, succulent, bayonet-shaped, margin with reddish spines or serratures; flowers racemose or spicate, ellowish, orange-red; stamens 6, unequal, 3 longer than corolla.

Insippated Juice: (A. vera): Curaçao, blackish-brown, opaque masses, fracture uneven, waxy, resinous.

Microscopic Characteristics

Powder [A. vera] reddish-brown, microscopically (in almond oil) ... reddish-brown irregular, angular more or less opaque fragments.

Source: Culbreth, D. (1917) *A Manual of Materia Media and Pharmacology*, 6th ed. [5]

Chemical Constituents

- 1) The three Aloin isomers Barbaloin, -barboloin, and Isobarbaloin, which make up the so-called "crystalline" Aloin and are found in the medication at concentrations of between 10 and 30%, are aloes' most important constituents. Aloe-emodin, resin, amor-phous Aloin, and emodin are additional components. All types include barbaloin, a crystalline glycoside that is slightly yellow in color, bitter, and water soluble.
- 3) Isobarbaloin is a crystalline substance, present in Curacao aloe and in trace amount in Cape aloe and absent in Socotrine and Zanzibar aloe.
- 4) The chief constituents of Socotrine and Zanzibar aloe are Barbaloin and β -Barbaloin.
- 5) Anthracene glycosides (11 to 43%)
- 6) Isobarbaloin, aloe-emodin and aloesone.
- 7) Aloinosides A and B (only in Cape aloes).
- 8) Also contains Aloetic acid, homonataloin etc.

Chemical Tests

Bring 1 gram of the drug to a boil in 100 milliliters of water, let it cool, then add 1 gram of kieselguhr, stir thoroughly, and strain through filter paper.

1. Borax Test: Add 0.5 g of borax to 10 ml of aloe solution, heat, and watch for the production of a

green fluorescence that indicates the presence of aloe-emodin anthranol.

2. Modified Anthraquinone Test: 0.1 g of medicine is mixed with 5 ml of a 5% solution of ferric chloride and 5 ml of diluted hydrochloric acid. The mixture is heated in a water bath for 5 to 6 minutes before cooling. the benzene or chloroform addition and stirring of an organic solvent. Add diluted ammonia to an equivalent volume of the organic solvent layer. Ammoniacal layer produces pinkish-red hue.

3. Bromine Test: Add an equal volume of bromine solution to 5 milliliters of aloe solution; a large, yellow precipitate forms as a result of the presence of tetrabromaloin.

4. Nitrous Acid Test: Add a small amount of sodium nitrite and a few drops of diluted acetic acid to 5 milliliters of aloe solution; the mixture turns pink or purplish in color.

5. Nitric Acid Test: 5 ml of aloe solution is mixed with 2 ml of concentrated nitric acid; Curacao aloe generates a deep reddish-brown color, Socotrine aloe produces a pale yellowish-brown color, Zanzibar aloe produces a yellowish-brown color, and Cape aloe initially produces a brown color that, when left to stand, turns into green.

6. Cupraloin Test: 1ml of the solution is diluted to 5ml with water and to it 1 drop of copper sulphate solution is added.

Functions of Aloes

It contains healthful plant compounds:

Aloe vera may help treat skin injuries.

Aloe vera is extensively used in the beauty, medicinal, and food diligence, and its monthly request worth is estimated at\$ 13 billion worldwide one trusted source. The thick, pointed, and meaty green leavesof aloe vera, which can reach a maximum length of 12 – 19 elevation(30 – 50 centimeters), are its most distinctive point. Because each splint has a muddy membrane that holds water, the leaves are thick. The" gel" that consumers generally associate with aloe vera products is this water- filled towel. The maturity of the factory's salutary bioactive constituents, including vitamins, minerals, amino acids, and antioxidants, are present in the gel.

1. It has antioxidant and antibacterial properties

Antioxidants are essential to one's health. Strong antioxidants found in Trusted Source aloe vera gel come from the large family of composites known as polyphenols. These polyphenols help prevent the growth of certain bacteria that can harm human conditions, along with a number of other compounds found in aloe vera. The antibacterial, antiviral, and antiseptic goods of aloe vera are well- known. Because of this it might prop in crack mending and the treatment of skin conditions.

2. It accelerates wound healing

Instead of being digested, aloe vera is most usually applied externally to the skin as medicine. It has really been used for a very long time to cure burns, especially sunburn. As early as 1810–1820, aloe vera preparations were described as a skin protectant in the United States Pharmacopeia.

It is a good topical burn treatment for first- and second-degree burns, according to research. For instance, when compared to normal care, a review of experimental research revealed that aloe vera could cut the time it took for burns to heal by around 9 days. Additionally, it helped to prevent infections, itching, and redness. The research shows that aloe vera can cure a variety of wounds, despite conflicting knowledge to the contrary.

3.It reduces dental plaque

Health problems including tooth decay and gum disease are fairly common. One of the greatest ways to prevent the emergence of these conditions is to reduce the amount of plaque or bacterial biofilms that build on the teeth. In a mouthwash trial of 300 healthy persons, researchers compared chlorhexidine, a popular ingredient in mouthwash, with 100% pure aloe vera juice. After 4 days of use, the aloe vera mouthwash seems to be just as effective at removing teeth plaque as chlorhexidine.

4.It helps treat canker sores

Canker sores, also known as mouth ulcers, are a common occurrence throughout people's lifetimes. These typically appear inside the mouth and beneath the lip, lasting roughly a week. Reliable Source. Research has indicated that using aloe vera therapy helps hasten the healing process of oral ulcers. For instance, an aloe vera patch applied to the affected area for seven days helped reduce the size of 180 people's recurrent mouth ulcers (Trusted Source). It did not, however, perform any better than corticosteroids, the standard treatment for ulcers. Aloe vera gel lessened the pain that accompanied oral ulcers in addition to hastening their healing.

5. It reduces constipation

Constipation may also be relieved with aloe vera. This time, the advantages come from the latex rather than the gel. The yellow, sticky substance that lies just beneath the leaf's skin is called latex.

Aloin, also known as barbaloin, is the main laxative component that causes this effect. But with frequent use, some have voiced worries about safety. Because of this, aloe latex has not been sold as an over-the-counter drug in the United States. In contrast to common perception, aloe vera doesn't seem to work well for other digestive disorders including inflammatory bowel disease or irritable bowel syndrome.

6. It might prevent wrinkles and enhance skin.

Topical aloe vera gel appears to have some potential benefits in delaying skin aging. Over the course of 90 days, oral aloe vera gel supplementation enhanced collagen formation and improved skin suppleness in a 2009 study (Trusted Source) involving 30 females over 45. Aloe vera may also help the skin retain moisture and strengthen its integrity, which may aid with dry skin issues, according to Reviews Trusted Source.

Read more about aloe vera's effects on the skin here:

- aloe vera for acne
- aloe vera for psoriasis
- aloe vera for eczema

7. It lowers blood sugar levels:

Aloe vera is occasionally used as a diabetes treatment. This is due to the possibility that it will increase blood sugar regulation and insulin sensitivity. For instance, due to its effects on glycemic management, aloe vera may be beneficial for those with type 2 diabetes or prediabetes, according to a review Trusted Source of eight studies. Nevertheless, due to the subpar quality of the already available research, scientists do not now advise utilizing aloe vera for this reason.

8. Risks:

With few known adverse effects, aloe vera is a safe remedy. Topical use is probably safe, according to the National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH)Trusted Source.

However, because of its laxative properties, taking aloe vera orally can result in diarrhea or cramping in the stomach. Additionally, there have been some reports (Trusted Source) linking long-term use of aloe vera supplements to liver damage. Non decolorized whole leaf extract of aloe vera appears to be linked to a higher risk of cancer in rats, according to the NCCIH Trusted Source as well.

Pharmacological Activity

The most well-known use of aloe vera is for treating burns and other wounds. By encouraging cell proliferation, aloe vera applied topically to a wound promotes both the rate of closure and the tensile strength of the wound (Fig. 5). It accomplishes this by quickening the blood flow to the injured area. The best wound dressing that has ever been found is aloe. The following mechanism explains this acceleration: Aloe vera gel promotes increased collagen cross-linking and content in the wound, which leads to improved scar tissue breakage and wound contraction. Chithra et al. also documented an increase in hyaluronic acid and dermatan sulphate content in the granulating tissue of wounds that were healing. In human keratinocyte monolayers, kDa glycoprotein

isolated from

A. vera increased epithelial cell migration and improved the healing process of wounds.

a. Anti-Fungal: Aloe vera has anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, antibacterial, and hypoglycemic qualities, according to in vitro and animal research using whole leaf extract. The antifungal qualities of aloe vera extract have been demonstrated by numerous studies.

b. Anti Inflammatory: The results of the chemical tests for anthraquinones and sterols type delta 5 in the chloroform extract were positive. These findings revealed the anti-inflammatory properties of aloe vera gel extracts and implied their cyclooxygenase-mediated inhibition of the arachidonic acid pathway.

c. Anti- Microbial: Using the cup plate diffusion method, the antimicrobial activity of aloe vera extract was evaluated against pathogenic bacteria such as Staphylococcus aureus, Klebisella pneumonia, and E. coli, as well as fungi like Aspergillus niger and Candida at doses of 1:20 mg/ml and 2:40 mg/ml.

Marketed Preparation From Aloes

Chemical Name	Brand Name	Image of product
Aloevera Gel	Oriflame	
Jeevani Tablets	Aadar	

Aloeberry Nectar	Forever	
Aloe plus	Herbalife	
Wound Healing Cream	Element	
Piles Away	IMC	

Uses And Side Effects

- It is used to treat painful inflammatory manifestations and possesses purgative properties.
- Friar's balsam, or compound tincture of benzoin, is made with it as an ingredient.
- Aloe gel is applied topically to radiation burns to relieve pain and itching right away.
- Usually used in conjunction with carminatives.
- It can be found in some desserts, yogurt, lotions, and drinks.
- Skin wounds are treated with it.
- It lessens warts, rosacea, and psoriasis.
- It also lessens wrinkles and signs of aging.
- It also lessens dermatitis.
- It facilitates increased flexibility.
- It also possesses the ability to regenerate body cells.
- It encourages bowel movement in those who are constipated.
- Aids in the healing of fungal infections, rashes, sores, and insect bite

Clinical uses: The clinical use of aloe vera is supported substantially by anecdotal data. Though utmost of these uses are intriguing, controlled trials are essential to determine its effectiveness in all the following conditions.^{22,23}

a. Uses based on scientific evidence: These uses have been tested in humans or creatures. Safety and effectiveness haven't always been proven.

Conditions: Seborrheic dermatitis,²⁴ psoriasis vulgaris,^{25,26} genital herpes,^{27,28} skin burns,^{5,29} diabetes (type 2),³⁰ HIV infection,³¹ cancer prevention,^{32,33} ulcerative colitis³⁴ wound healing (results of aloe on wound healing are mixed with some studies reporting positive results³⁵ and others showing no benefit³⁶ or potential worsening^{37,38}), pressure ulcers,³⁶ mucositis,³⁹ radiation dermatitis,⁴⁰ acne vulgaris,⁴¹ lichen planus,⁴² frostbite,⁴³ aphthous stomatitis,⁴⁴ and constipation.¹⁷

b. Uses based on tradition or theory: The uses listed below are derived from scientific theories or customs. Their safety and efficacy haven't always been established, and they haven't always been extensively tested on humans.

Conditions include tic douloureux, systemic lupus erythematosus, alopecia, bacterial and fungal skin infections, chronic leg wounds, and parasitic infections.

c. Adulteration: Glycerin, glucose, sucrose, and maltodextrin are frequently used as adulterants in aloe vera. Malic acid is another adulterant in it.

Side effects

a. Topical: It can cause burning, stinging, redness, and in rare instances, generalized dermatitis in sensitive individuals. The majority of allergic reactions are brought on by anthraquinones, such as aloin and barbaloin. It is best to apply it to a small area first to check for any potential allergic reactions.

b. Oral: Constipation getting worse, diarrhea, red urine, hepatitis, abdominal pain, and cramping. Long-term use has been linked to an increased risk

of colorectal cancer. Electrolyte imbalances could be caused by low potassium levels as a result of a laxative effect.

c. Contraindication: Contraindicated in cases of known allergy to plants in the Liliaceae family.

d. Pregnancy and breastfeeding: It is not recommended to take oral aloe during pregnancy due to the possibility that it may cause uterine contractions. Furthermore, it can sometimes result in gastrointestinal distress in the nursing child of the mother.

e. Interactions:

Aloe vera applied topically can enhance the skin's absorption of steroid creams, such as hydrocortisone. Digoxin's effectiveness is reduced and its side effects may worsen due to its potassium-lowering effect. Combining aloe vera with furosemide may raise the risk of potassium depletion. It may interact with insulin and oral hypoglycemic medications because it lowers blood sugar. Because of this, some of the many uses and benefits of aloe vera may just be folklore and some may actually be magic. Eventually, controlled studies will be required to prove aloe vera's effectiveness in a variety of circumstances.

10. Current Information Of Aloes

In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that medicinal plants are used globally, and that the laws governing their appropriate use such as those pertaining to the concentration and purity of necessary chemical compounds—are widely accepted. Over the past three decades, the use of herbal medicine products has grown significantly, and at least 80% of people worldwide now rely on them for some aspect of their primary healthcare (Martins Ekor, 2013). As quality and improvement analysis, as well as advantages in clinical research, demonstrate the usefulness of herbal medicine in both treating and preventing illness, it is becoming more widely accepted (K. P. Sampath Kumar, Debjit Bhowmik, 2010). One of the most frequent emergencies is

ethanol ingestion with alcoholic intoxication, which is often followed by alcohol withdrawal syndrome in chronic alcoholics who come to the Accordingly, Aloe Vera (*Aloebarbadensis*) is the most widely used medicinal plant in the world and the oldest known medicinal plant. According to Joe Leech (2017), the leaves of this plant are covered in a gel-like substance that is packed full of vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and amino acids, among other beneficial compounds. Another study looked into the hepatoprotective properties of aloe vera polysaccharides against chronic alcohol-induced liver damage in mice. According to this study, AVGP (*A. vera* polysaccharides) has a strong protective effect against long-term alcohol use.

11. Effects of Oral Administration of Aloe Vera Plus on the Heart and Kidney:

Subacute Toxicity Study in Rat Models:

After receiving 0.2 ml of Aloe vera plus twice daily for 14 days, 3 out of 5 rats (60%) showed signs of nephrotoxicity, as evidenced by persistent inflammatory cell infiltration of the tubules and interstitium. Three (60%) and two (40%) of the five rats who received 0.4 milliliters twice a day showed signs of nephrotoxicity. Two of the three rats that showed toxic consequences had chronic infiltration of inflammatory cells, and the third experienced tubule collapse, tubular injury, and parenchymal hemorrhage. Three of the five rats that received 0.8 ml twice a day showed signs of nephrotoxicity on histology, including tubular necrosis, collapse, hyalinization, and intra-parenchymal hemorrhage in one animal and chronic inflammatory cell infiltration in another. Following 28 days of Aloe vera plus treatment, 3 out of 5 rats (or 60%) who got 0.2 ml twice daily experienced nephrotoxicity, with 1 exhibiting interstitial fibrosis and the other 2 showing thickening of the renal vascular wall and chronic inflammatory cell infiltration. Nephrotoxicity was not present in two (40%) of the animals.

Three (60%) of the five rats who were given 0.4 milliliters twice a day showed signs of severe nephrotoxicity, or kidney injury, which was characterized by widespread glomerular and interstitial fibrosis, tubular necrosis, and tubule hyalinization. Of the rats, 2 (or 40%) exhibited no signs of nephrotoxicity. Two (40%) of the five rats who received 0.8 milliliters twice a day had tubular necrosis and chronic inflammatory cell infiltration, which were indicators of nephrotoxicity. (20)

Aloe extract inhibits porcine epidemic diarrhea virus in vitro and in vivo:

In vitro inhibition of viral infection test After inoculating confluent Vero or IPEC-J2 cell monolayers in 12-well plates with varying concentrations of Ae (4–16 mg/mL) or the control normal DMEM for one hour, the cells were infected with PEDV at a MOI of 0.2–0.4 for an additional hour. The viral inoculums were then removed, and new maintenance medium containing various concentrations of Ae was added. Cells were fixed for the indirect immunofluorescent experiment, as explained below, twenty-four hours later. Cells were harvested at the designated 12-, 24-, and 48-hour intervals. Cell lysates were then made and subjected to Western Blot analysis, as detailed below, or TCID₅₀ analysis was used to quantify the viral titers in the cell lysates in order to compute PFU, as previously mentioned. (21)

CONCLUSION

Aloe vera and its compounds have qualities that make them useful for preserving the integrity and moisture of the skin as well as preventing ulcers. Aloe vera seems to have the potential to enhance wound healing and advance societal health when used in conjunction with other therapeutic approaches.

REFERENCES

1. B. Pomahač, T. Svensjö, F. Yao, H. Brown, and E. Eriksson, —Tissue engineering of

- skin,|| *Critical Reviews in Oral Biology and Medicine*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 333–334
2. H. G. Bingham, D. Hudson, and J. Popp, —A retrospective review of the burn intensive care unit admissions for a year,|| *Journal of Burn Care & Rehabilitation*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 56–58
 3. V. McGill, A. Kowal-Vern, S. G. Fisher, S. Kahn, and R. L. Gamelli, —The impact of substance use on mortality and morbidity from thermal injury,|| *Journal of Trauma: Injury, Infection & Critical Care*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 931–934,
 4. T. Blanks, S. Brown, B. Cosgruve et al., *The Body Shop Book of Wellbeing Mind, Body, and Soul*, Ebury Press, London, UK, 1998.
 5. Y. Iba, A. Shibata, M. Kato, and T. Masukawa, —Possible involvement of mast cells in collagen remodeling in the late phase of cutaneous wound healing in mice,|| *International Immunopharmacology*, vol. 4, no. 14, pp. 1873–1880
 6. P. Martin, —Wound healing—aiming for perfect skin regeneration,|| *Science*, vol. 276
 7. N. Ganapathy, S. S. Venkataraman, R. Daniel, R. J. Aravind, and V. B. Kumarakrishnan, —Molecular biology of wound healing,|| *Journal of Pharmacy & Bioallied Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 6, supplement 2, pp. 334–337
 8. J. O. Hollinger, C. E. Hart, S. N. Hirsch, S. Lynch, and G. E. Friedlaender, —Recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor: biology and clinical applications,|| *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery— American Volume*, vol. 90, no. 1, pp. 48–54
 9. S. Barrientos, O. Stojadinovic, M. S. Golinko, H. Brem, and M. Tomic-Canic, —Growth factors and cytokines in wound healing,|| *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 585–601
 10. F. Chablais and A. Jaźwińska, —IGF signaling between blastema and wound epidermis is required for fin regeneration,|| *Development*, vol. 137, no. 6, pp. 871–879,
 11. S. Werner and R. Grose, —Regulation of wound healing by growth factors and cytokines,|| *Physiological Reviews*, vol. 83, no. 3, pp. 835–870, M. S. Bitar and Z. N. Labbad, —Transforming growth factor- β and insulin-like growth factor-I in relation to diabetes-induced impairment of wound healing,|| *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 113–119,
 12. M. H. Gartner, J. D. Benson, and M. D. Caldwell, —Insulin-like growth factors I and II expression in the healing wound,|| *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 389–394, 1992
 13. M. S. Bitar, —Insulin and glucocorticoid-dependent suppression of the IGF-I system in diabetic wounds,|| *Surgery*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 687–695.
 14. M. S. Bitar and Z. N. Labbad, —Transforming growth factor- β and insulin-like growth factor-I in relation to diabetes-induced impairment of wound healing,|| *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 113–119,
 15. M. H. Gartner, J. D. Benson, and M. D. Caldwell, —Insulin-like growth factors I and II expression in the healing wound,|| *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 389–394, 1992
 16. M. S. Bitar, —Insulin and glucocorticoid-dependent suppression of the IGF-I system in diabetic wounds,|| *Surgery*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 687–695,
 17. M. S. Bitar and Z. N. Labbad, —Transforming growth factor- β and insulin-like growth factor-I in relation to diabetes-induced impairment of wound healing,|| *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 113–119,

18. M. H. Gartner, J. D. Benson, and M. D. Caldwell, —Insulin-like growth factors I and II expression in the healing wound, *Journal of Surgical Research*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 389–394, 1992
19. M. S. Bitar, —Insulin and glucocorticoid-dependent suppression of the IGF-I system in diabetic wounds, *Surgery*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 687–695,
20. Boudreau MD, Beland FA . An evaluation of the biological and toxicological properties of *Aloe barbadensis miller (Aloe vera)*. *J Environ Sci Health C Environ Carcinog Ecotoxicol Rev*, 2006; 24 (1): 103-154
21. Xu, Z., Zhang, Y., Gong, L., Huang, L., Lin, Y., Qin, J., Du, Y., Zhou, Q., Xue, C., Cao, Y. 2019 Isolation and characterization of a highly pathogenic strain of Porcine enteric alphacoronavirus causing watery diarrhoea and high mortality in newborn piglets. *Transbound. Emerg. Dis.* 66, 119–130.

HOW TO CITE: Sandip Gorade*, Sonali Kalam, Dr. Gajanan Sanap, Review Article On Medicinal Plant Aloe, *Int. J. in Pharm. Sci.*, 2023, Vol 1, Issue 11, 611-624. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10219050>

